

(a)

Indianoinocellia mayana

(b)

Inocellia elegans

Fig. S1. Images of antennae of inocelliids

Fig. S2. Images of head and pronotum of snakeflies

(a) *Inocellia tibetana*

(b) *Amurinocellia sinensis*

(c) *Fibla pasiphae*

(d) *Sininocellia chikun*

(e) *Xanthostigma gobicola*

(f) *Agulla arizonica*

Fig. S3. Images of wings of snakeflies

Fig. S4. Drawings of male fused gonocoxites 11 (gonarcus) of inocelliids

Parainocellia bicolor
(a)

Fibla pasiphae
(b)

Negha inflata
(c)

Parainocellia braueri
(d)

Fibla peyerimhoffi
(e)

Negha inflata
(f)

Parainocellia resslii
(g)

Fibla maclachlani
(h)

Negha meridionalis
(i)

Epinocellia burmana
(j)

Fibla hesperica
(k)

Negha longicornis
(l)

Indianoinocellia pilicornis
(m)

Amurinocellia calida
(n)

Sininocellia gigantos
(o)

Fig. S5. Drawings of male fused gonocoxites 11 (gonarcus) of inocelliids

Inocellia obtusangularis

(a)

Inocellia yunnanica

(d)

Inocellia bilobata

(f)

Inocellia cornuta

(h)

Amurinocellia sinensis

(j)

Inocellia fujiana

(b)

Inocellia longispina

(e)

Inocellia striata

(g)

Inocellia shinohara

(i)

Inocellia rara

(k)

Inocellia hainanica

(c)

Fig. S6. Drawings of male fused gonocoxites 11 (gonarcus) of inocelliids

Fig. S7. Maximum likelihood tree based on PCG123 dataset

Fig. S8. Bayesian inference tree based on PCG123 dataset

Fig. S9. Maximum parsimony tree based on PCG123 dataset

Fig. S10. Maximum likelihood tree based on PCG123rRNA dataset

Fig. S11. Bayesian inference tree based on PCG123rRNA dataset

Fig. S12. Maximum parsimony tree based on PCG123rRNA dataset

Fig. S13. Maximum likelihood tree based on PCG12 dataset

Fig. S14. Bayesian inference tree based on PCG12 dataset

Fig. S15. Maximum parsimony tree based on PCG12 dataset

Fig. S16. Bayesian inference tree based on PCG_AA dataset

Fig. S17. Maximum parsimony tree based on PCG_AA dataset

Fig. S18. Bayesian inference tree based on the combined analysis of morphological and molecular data.

Fig. S19. Maximum parsimony tree based on the combined analysis of morphological and molecular data.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. S20. BEAST divergence times estimates for key nodes in inocelliid cladogenesis (node codes correspond to those in Fig. 4), under different priors Violin plots presenting mean ages (white dots) along with the posterior distribution (blue area) of the 95% credibility intervals (black bars) inferred in the different BEAST analyses.